

MODERN ETIOLOGICAL AND PATHOGENETIC FACTORS OF OBESITY IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

Ergasheva Muharram Uktamovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6673005>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

*obesity, children,
adolescents, metabolic
syndrome, pathogenesis*

ABSTRACT

This review article is devoted to the mechanisms of formation and pathogenetic links of metabolic syndrome and obesity in pediatric patients. The article summarizes the research of foreign authors and analyzes the important points of the pathogenesis of this pathology.

Today, obesity is an urgent problem for the whole world, which is associated with its progressive spread. WHO experts suggest a twofold increase in the number of obese people by 2025 compared to 2000. Today, more than a billion people on the planet have excess body weight [4,9].

This trend is due to the fact that the economic crisis has led to a change in the diet (cheaper, carbohydrate-containing products prevail, which entails an overstrain of the adaptive mechanisms of the digestive system and the formation of prenosological conditions). The leading pathogenetic mechanism of exogenous (alimentary) obesity is the discrepancy between the incoming volume of food and the energy consumption of the body. This imbalance induces an acceleration of adipocyte growth and, as a consequence, an increase in body weight. However, this process can also be associated with metabolic defects caused by "breakdowns" of enzyme systems, as well as with leptin

hyperproduction [1], which can determine the accumulation of triglycerides in adipocytes even with a normal diet. In addition, the increased deposition of lipids creates conditions for the occurrence of atherosclerotic manifestations at an early age [9, 23].

With the understanding that obesity is accompanied by a significant number of various complications, interest in the causes of obesity is also increasing. In this regard, an active search is underway for biologically active substances (most often hormones) and genes encoding their synthesis at different stages. However, it is not possible to find any one substance or one gene that would determine the development of obesity. Therefore, currently, among the main causes of obesity, both genetic, hormonal factors and diencephalic (hypothalamic obesity) are considered, and, of course, all this against the background of poor nutrition and lifestyle [21].

Childhood obesity entails both short-term and long-term adverse consequences for physical and psychosocial health, and is largely a risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, orthopedic problems and mental disorders. Taking into account WHO recommendations, obesity in children and adolescents should be defined as $+2.0$ sds BMI, and overweight – from $+1.0$ to $+2.0$ sds BMI [20].

The role of hereditary factors in the development of obesity is currently beyond doubt. The existence of familial forms of obesity is well known, in which the inheritance coefficient reaches 25%, which indicates a sufficiently high influence of genetic factors in the development of this disease [1]. To date, several monogenic forms of obesity are known and confirmed, which are caused by mutations of the leptin gene, its receptor gene, prohormone convertase-1, 4R-melanocortin receptor and proopiomelanocortin [11]. Clinical manifestations of monogenic variants are characterized by early onset of the disease, rapidly progressing course, morbid obesity, hyperphagia, secondary hypogonadism [6]. In the last two decades, much attention has been paid to the research of neuropeptide Y, its role in body weight control and appetite control [1,15,23]. Neuropeptide Y enhances food intake, because it causes a feeling of hunger, through the centers of hunger and satiety [3, 12]. The role of the endocannabinoid system (ES) in the development of obesity is actively discussed [8,15]. ES regulates the energy balance in the body at the main functional levels, which involve the limbic system, hypothalamus, gastrointestinal tract, adipose tissue. Exogenous and endogenous cannabinoids contribute to weight gain.

With obesity, there is an increased activity of ES [15,24]. Adiponectin is secreted in adipose tissue, which is involved in the regulation of energy homeostasis of the body [15]. The level of adiponectin increases with fasting and weight loss on the background of a low-calorie diet in obese people [12,14]. It was found that a low level of adiponectin in the blood precedes the development of IR [1, 13].

Hormonal factors of the development of obesity include an excess of corticosteroids, which may be iatrogenic or associated with hypersecretion of corticosteroids. This hypersecretion may be due to excessive secretion of ACTH, pathology of the adrenal glands. The clinical picture and hormonal-metabolic shifts depend on which hormones are secreted in excess. The most famous is the Itsenko—Cushing syndrome. Under this name, diseases caused by an excess of corticosteroids in the blood are combined. Clinical manifestations in children are obesity of the trunk, deposition of fat above the collarbones, on the neck and nape, a moon—shaped face, striae on the abdomen, chest and inner thighs, petechiae, bruising, arterial hypertension, impaired glucose tolerance, growth retardation [7, 12].

With a decrease in thyroid function (hypothyroidism), overweight or obesity is also noted, despite a reduced appetite. The development of pathology is caused either by reduced production of thyroid hormones, or by a decrease in their biological effect at the tissue level [5]

Recently, there is increasing evidence that obesity is an independent risk factor for developing chronic kidney disease (CKD). The basic body mass index (BMI) has been proposed as an independent predictor of

CKD progression [2]. Obesity is closely associated with the two most common causes of end-stage renal failure (ESRD), namely hypertension and diabetes mellitus. In addition, metabolic syndrome (MS), as the main consequence of obesity, is also an independent risk factor for ESRD [3]. Recent data also support the hypothesis that decreased insulin sensitivity and hyperinsulinemia are among the most important factors leading to kidney damage [14, 18].

Conclusion

The etiopathogenetic unity of complications of obesity, their threatening nature for the entire population and the high frequency of occurrence in childhood and adulthood led to the concept of metabolic syndrome. Over the past three

decades, there has been a sharp increase in the prevalence of metabolic syndrome worldwide. This is facilitated by a combination of a number of factors. Firstly, in most countries there has been a steady increase in the number of overweight and obese people. Secondly, some patients probably have a hereditary predisposition to the development of metabolic syndrome. This is also confirmed by the fact that in certain ethnic groups the frequency of metabolic syndrome is higher even in the absence of obesity. Despite the great importance of hereditary factors, the development of metabolic syndrome is also influenced by a sedentary lifestyle, which is aggravated in modern reality by the progression of urbanization and technological progress.

References:

1. List of literature Ergasheva M.U. (2022). Diagnostic Markers of Cardiovascular Complications after Covid-19. Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity, 4, 210-215. Retrieved from <http://sjii.indexedresearch.org/index.php/sjii/article/view/76>
2. Ganiyeva Sh.Sh., Jurayeva F.R., Hamdamova G.R. (2021). DIAGNOSTIC ROLE OF IMMUNOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN THE GASTROINTESTINAL FOOD ALLERGY IN CHILDREN. Art of Medicine International Medical Scientific Journal, Volume-1(Issue-2), 73-81. . <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5140474>
3. Ganiyeva Sh.Sh., Rustamov B.B., Panoyev X.Sh. REGIONAL FEATURES OF THE FREQUENCY AND CLINIC OF RESPIRATORY ALLERGY//New Day in Medicine 3(35)2021 194-197 <https://cutt.ly/hEqY6SK> <https://newdaymedicine.com/index.php/2021/09/16/37-3-35-2021-ganiyeva-sh-sh-rustamov-b-b-regional-features-of-the-frequency-and-clinic-of-respiratory-allergy/>
4. Juraeva Firuza Raxmatovna. (2022). MODERN ASPECTS OF THE PATHOGENESIS OF COMORBIDITY IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. World Bulletin of Public Health, 10, 52-54. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/943>
5. Navruzova Sh.I, & Kenjaeva I.M. (2022). MODERN ASPECTS OF THE STUDY OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN HYPERTENSION. World Bulletin of Public Health, 10, 48-51. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/942>
6. Navruzova Shakar Istamovna. (2022). HUMORAL IMMUNITY AND MARKERS OF INFLAMMATION IN THE PROGNOSIS OF COMPLICATIONS OF HYPERTENSION. World

- Bulletin of Public Health, 9, 139-141. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/852>
7. Panoev Xurshid Shuxratovich. (2022). PATHOGENETIC INTERACTION OF THYROID DISEASES AND GASTROINTESTINAL PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN. World Bulletin of Public Health, 9, 195-198. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/893>
8. Sarafidis PA, Ruilope LM. Insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia, and renal injury: mechanisms and implications. Am J Nephrol 2006; 26: 232-244
9. WHO. Ожирение и избыточный вес. Режим доступа: <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs311/ru/>
10. Wynne K., Stanley S., McGowan B., et al. // J. Endocrinol. — 2005. — Vol.184. — P.291-318.
11. Аверьянов А.П., Болотова И.В., Зотова С.А. Ожирение в детском возрасте. // Лечащий врач. — М., 2010. — №2. — С.13- 15.
12. Вербицкая О.Г., Попова В.А., Афонин А.А. и др. Клинико-диагностическое значение определения лептина и андрогенов у мальчиков и подростков с ожирением // Мед. вестн. юга России. – 2013; 2: 37–43. Попова В., Кожин А., Мегидь Ю., & Романова Е. (2016). ЭТИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА АЛИМЕНТАРНОГО ОЖИРЕНИЯ У ПОДРОСТКОВ. Врач, (12), 71-75.
13. Витебская А. В. Ожирение в детском возрасте: возможности применения американского консенсуса в российской практике // Ожирение и метаболизм. — 2009. — № 4. — С. 14 – 19.
14. Ганиева Ш.Ш. & Темиров М.Т. (2022). Оценка Иммунологических показателей при Гастроинтестинальной Патологии У Детей. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(2), 432-435. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZYR72>
15. Ганиева Ш.Ш., Раджабова Г.Б. Клинико-Лабораторная Оценка Состояния Здоровья Больных Хронической Обструктивной Болезнью Легких, Перенесших Коронавирусную Инфекцию. CAJMNS [Internet]. 2021Oct.18 [cited 2021Oct.28];:76-0. Available from: <http://cajmns.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJMNS/article/view/353>
16. Дедов И.И., Петеркова В.А. Детская эндокринология. — М.: Универсум Пабблишинг, 2006. — С. 448-475.
17. Дедов И. И., Мельниченко Г. А., Пронин В. С. и др. Клиника и диагностика эндокринных нарушений. — М. — Тверь: Триада, 2005. — 248 с.
18. Жураева Ф.Р., Колесникова Н.В., Ганиева Ш.Ш. СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИММУННЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИИ // Евразийский вестник педиатрии. — 2021; 3 (10): 7-13. <https://cutt.ly/ARsAPWu>
19. Загоруйко, М. В., Бардымова, Т. П., & Рычкова, Л. В. (2010). Ожирение у детей и подростков. Сибирский медицинский журнал (Иркутск), 97 (6), 16-19.
20. Загоруйко, М. В., Бардымова, Т. П., & Рычкова, Л. В. (2010). Ожирение у детей и подростков. Сибирский медицинский журнал (Иркутск), 97 (6), 16-19.
21. Петеркова В.А, Ремизов О.В. Ожирение в детском возрасте. // Ожирение и метаболизм. — М., 2004. — №1. — С. 17- 23.

22. Петросян Эдита Константиновна, Костерева Екатерина Александровна, Новиков Сергей Юрьевич, Морено Илья Геннадьевич, & Шумилов Петр Валентинович (2017). Функциональное состояние почек у подростков с ожирением. Нефрология, 21 (2), 48-55.
23. Солнцева А.В., Сукало А.В. Ожирение у детей. Вопросы этиологии и патогенеза. // Мед. новости. — Минск, 2008. — №3. — С. 7-13.
24. Щербакова, М. Ю., Порядина, Г. И., & Ковалева, Е. А. (2010). Проблема ожирения в детском возрасте. Экспериментальная и клиническая гастроэнтерология, (7), 74-82.